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Linguistics in Vanuatu 45 years after Independence

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Linguistics in Vanuatu 45 years after Independence

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Abstract

This article gives an overview of the progress of linguistic research and other language work in Vanuatu. Using a database of resources in and about Vanuatu languages, we first investigate grammatical descriptions, lexical descriptions and other types of linguistic research about Vanuatu's Oceanic languages, discussing patterns in regional coverage and progress over time. We then focus on two types of texts that are particularly important to language documentation and language planning in Vanuatu: annotated multimedia corpora and Bible translations. We also briefly discuss research on Vanuatu's official languages, Bislama, English and French. We see strong regional effects in coverage of Vanuatu languages, emphasising the importance of community and researcher networks. Languages of Vanuatu's two largest and most linguistically diverse islands, Espiritu Santo and Malekula, are the least researched. Overall, our investigation shows steady progress in documentation and analysis of Vanuatu's languages over the past seventy years, with occasional declines in response to specific events like the Covid-19 pandemic.

Summary in Bislama

Long Vanuatu i gat ova long 100 difren lanwis, be fulap long ol lanwis ia i no gat wok yet long olketa long saed blong dokumentesen mo deskripsen, olsem ol dikseneri, grama, koleksen blong ol storian o Baebol translesen. Yet i gat plante lanwis tu we ol man oli bin priperem ol materiel olsem finis, stat long ol miseneri fastaem kasem tede we fulap lingwis, Baebol transleta mo ol komiuniti memba, oli stap mekem plante wok long saed blong ol lanwis. Long atikel ia mifala i wantem soem wanem we oli bin mekem finis, mo wanem wok i stap yet blong mekem. Mifala i soem wanem lanwis long Vanuatu we i gat wan dikseneri, wan grama, wan koleksen blong ol storian mo ol narafala teks, Baebol translesen, mo ol narafala risej long saed blong ol lanwis ia. Mifala i raetem atikol ia from mifala i wantem luk se wanem lanwis mo wanem aelan long Vanuatu oli nidim moa wok long fiuja.

Ol risal blong mifala i soem se sam lanwis oli gat plante dokumentesen, deskripsen, translesen mo risej, be sam narafala lanwis oli nogat nating. Santo hem i aelan blong Vanuatu we i gat tumas wok yet blong mekem i bitim ol narafala aelan, be i gat plante wok yet blo mekem tu long evri aelan long saed blong lanwis. Mifala i inkludum wan longfala list blong ol wok we oli bin mekem finis, mo ol map we man i save lukluk gud wanem lanwis i gat wanem kaen wok long hem finis. Kaen wok ia hem i bin go antap plante stat long araon 1950, be espeseli afta long 1995. Hem i wan gudfala samting be wok we i stap yet hem i plante we i plante. Mifala i hop se plante lingwis, transleta mo ol komiuniti memba bae oli kontiniu gudfala wok blong olgeta we oli bin mekem, mo tu bae ol niufala jeneresen i folem gudfala rod mo fasin blong olgeta, blong mekem sua se ol lanwis blong Vanuatu bae oli laev i stap blong ol fiuja jeneresen long Vanuatu.

Keywords

Language documentation and description, descriptive grammars, dictionaries, corpora, Vanuatu

1 Introduction

The sheer extent of linguistic diversity in Vanuatu makes documenting, describing and researching its languages a huge endeavour, requiring the efforts of many people over many generations. As 2025 marks the 45th anniversary of the country's Independence, this paper takes stock of the linguistic work that has been done on Vanuatu languages until today. We aim to answer the following questions: What is the state of documentation of different Vanuatu languages and groups of languages? What are the major and minor gaps? What trends can be observed in the progress of linguistic research on Vanuatu languages?

The earliest available linguistic data on Vanuatu languages was gathered by travellers from Europe surveying the area for prospective colonisation from the late 1700s onwards. The earliest records of specific Vanuatu languages appear to be the short wordlists of Lamap and a language of Tanna as an appendix to Forster's (1778) ethnographic account of Captain Cook's second voyage, which largely aims to categorise people into races and states of civilisation. Later, with the arrival of European missionaries, traders, and other outsiders to the New Hebrides in the second half of the 19th century, work on the languages of Vanuatu focused on producing translations of religious texts. These missionary projects produced the first detailed descriptions of the lexicon and the grammar of particular Vanuatu languages, such as grammar sketches written by Robert Codrington, Sidney Ray, Daniel Macdonald and others. For some of these missionary-scholars, tracking a relationship between Oceanic languages and Biblical languages was a major motivation for their linguistic endeavours. For example, some of Daniel Macdonald's work aimed to prove a relationship with Semitic languages.

Work by academic linguists increased significantly in the second half of the 20th century, including the seminal 1976 *New Hebrides Languages: An Internal Classification* by Darrell Tryon, which not only collected data on varieties covering the entire archipelago, but also systematically catalogued the linguistic diversity of Vanuatu for the first time. Arthur Capell, John Lynch, Terry Crowley, Jean-Michel Charpentier, Jean-Claude Rivierre, Robert Early, Ross Clark, Lamont Lindstrom, Albert Schütz, Jacques Guy, David Walsh, Wolfgang Sperlich and others helped set the stage for ongoing linguistic research in Vanuatu. The first women linguists working in Vanuatu – Miriam Meyerhoff, Dorothy

Jauncey and Catriona Malau – began their research in the country towards the end of the twentieth century.¹

Since the turn of the millennium, the number of linguists working on Vanuatu languages has grown considerably, including the first ni-Vanuatu trained linguists, Hannah Vari-Bogiri, Helen Tamtam, Lana Takau, Joel Simo, Carol Aru, Jim Gure and Reuben Tarihehe. The Vanuatu Cultural Centre has played a substantial role in regulating and coordinating linguistic research in Vanuatu and thousands of speakers of Vanuatu languages have been actively involved in language work, not least through the massively successful *Filwoka* Programme of the Vanuatu Cultural Centre (Regenvanu, 2011). *Kastom* schools promote local languages in various places including Southwest Bay (Malekula), Iatakwei (South Tanna), Turaga (Northeast Pentecost), Pango and Eton (Efate). These schools are run by local leaders and community members.

Lynch (1994)² and Lynch and Crowley (2001) published collections of works on Vanuatu languages and estimates of levels of documentation, description and research. Adelaar (2010, pp. 36–38) surveys additional documentation projects in progress in Vanuatu at the time. Partly in response to their calls for action, much more linguistic work on Vanuatu’s languages has been done since these works were published. This increase in linguistic research has been encouraged and facilitated by the Vanuatu Cultural Centre and other national institutions, as well as a global push for documentation and support for Indigenous languages. Growing international awareness of language endangerment has prompted fresh urgency and made new funding streams available for linguistic research in Vanuatu.

International databases like Glottolog (Hammarström et al., 2024), Ethnologue (Eberhard et al., 2023) and OLAC (Bird & Simons, 2001) have tracked the progress of language endangerment, documentation and resources available for languages across the world. Glottoscope (Hammarström et al., 2018) offers an overview of the state of documentation of languages all over the world (including Vanuatu), based on references in Glottolog’s reference database. Our investigation takes a similar approach to tracking the progress of linguistic research in Vanuatu, though taking a more fine-grained view based on an expanded bibliography.

Many speakers of Vanuatu languages are aware that their languages are relatively neglected in terms of documentation, description and research, and especially development of writing systems. For languages that have received little linguistic attention, it can be difficult to identify or access existing research. Both lack of linguistic research and lack of access to existing resources can impede grassroots language activism. We hope that this article, and the associated database of linguistic research on Vanuatu languages, can support community members to find linguistic resources and see their own language in a national perspective. Communities who know what has been done, what could be done and what remains to be done are more able to meaningfully engage in language planning and guide linguistic research to support their goals.³

¹ They were preceded by a number of women anthropologists who have published on linguistic topics from the 1970s onwards, such as Janet Dixon Keller, Ellen Facey and Margaret Jolly.

² Also available as an online bibliography by Nick Thieberger (1999).

³ The issue of communities’ access to materials is a very important one and there is a lot of room for improvement. For example, grammatical descriptions (§3) are normally written for a strictly academic audience, though it is possible to create community grammars, which are best integrated in more organised vernacular education efforts (e.g. the Kulu Language Institute in the Solomon Islands, McDougall & Zobule, 2021). Dictionaries (§4) may not last long in printed form in Vanuatu’s climate, but with increased

We also hope that this work can be useful for Vanuatu's authorities in their national policy planning and implementation. According to Vanuatu's National Sustainable Development Plan 2016–2030, the 2030 target is to increase the proportion of documented endangered languages in Vanuatu by 50% (DSPPAC, 2017). Finally, linguists and funding bodies can use the results of this investigation to inform their research priorities.

The article begins by explaining our methodology in section 2, before discussing research on the Indigenous Oceanic languages of Vanuatu. We look at grammar sketches and reference grammars in section 3, wordlists and dictionaries in section 4, and other kinds of linguistic research in section 5. In section 6 we discuss texts in these languages, focusing on two genres that are especially important to language documentation and community literacy: annotated multimedia corpora and Bible translations. In section 7, we briefly discuss the languages that were introduced to Vanuatu via colonisation and are now used across Vanuatu in institutional contexts and as lingua francas. For Bislama we explore grammatical and lexical description, other research and text types, while for English and French we look at research that investigates how the languages are used in Vanuatu. We conclude with a summary of the current state of linguistic research in Vanuatu.

2 Methodology

To investigate the current state of linguistic research in Vanuatu, we aimed to identify as many works as possible that involve documentation, description, and other forms of linguistic research involving Vanuatu languages. Our investigation is therefore based on the VanBib database, a newly compiled bibliography of works in and about Vanuatu languages. In addition to research, we have included texts in Vanuatu languages which may be part of documentation, Bible translation or other projects, as these are important resources for language communities. The database is included in the supplementary materials to this article, and will be continually updated as an open access resource on Zenodo. The VanBib database currently contains 3593 entries.⁴

The VanBib database builds on earlier attempts to track research on Vanuatu languages, using Lynch and Crowley's (2001) bibliography as well as references listed in the body of that work. The database also includes entries relevant to Vanuatu languages from the cross-linguistic Glottolog database (Hammarström et al., 2024), which aims to track research on all languages. The VanBib database is further updated with references contributed by colleagues working across Vanuatu. To ensure reverse compatibility, we have retained relevant fields from the Glottolog data, and added some additional fields related to VanBib metadata and notes, especially the addition of a subtype column to distinguish the length of wordlists and grammar sketches. In some cases, we have corrected or regularised labels from the source databases to ensure that labels are systematically applied in line with the categorisations presented in the following sections. More information about VanBib can be found in its documentation in the supplementary material.

Having gathered as much data as possible about linguistic research in Vanuatu, we aim to summarise and present the data to address our research questions. The VanBib database has allowed us to present a detailed picture of grammatical descriptions (i.e. reference

smartphone usage, dictionary apps may be one solution to improving access to dictionaries. Annotated corpora, even when deposited with open access in language archives, or at the Vanuatu Cultural Centre, are in practice often inaccessible to most community members.

⁴ Some entries, especially wordlists within larger resources, are duplicated for each language described in a source.

grammars and grammar sketches), lexical descriptions (i.e. dictionaries and wordlists), and other kinds of academic linguistic research outputs. We present data for these categories geographically in maps to observe trends for regional groups of languages (see Thieberger, 2014 for an earlier attempt to chart progress in language documentation of Vanuatu languages cartographically). In Vanuatu, genealogical subgroups of languages largely cluster geographically, (apart from the three Polynesian outlier languages: Fakamae, Ifira-Mele, and Futuna-Aniwa). Geographical proximity is also a reasonable proxy for the influence of long-term language contact in linkages across Vanuatu (Lynch, 2001; Lynch, Ross & Crowley, 2002, pp. 92–120; François, 2014). Due to social networks between communities and researchers, and the practicalities of conducting fieldwork, linguistic research also proceeds along regional lines. When discussing regions of Vanuatu we usually refer to provinces, but for Malampa province we distinguish Malekula from Ambrym-Paama, as Malekula has far greater linguistic diversity and lower coverage. We also present patterns in the publication of research in these genres over time, to show the historical development of linguistic research on Vanuatu languages. All statistics, figures and maps were generated using R (R Core Team, 2025) in RStudio (Posit team, 2025).

The VanBib database also contains many texts in the languages of Vanuatu, including written, audio-recorded, and video-recorded texts. While we hope that this enables community members to find and access all kinds of texts in their languages, these types of entries are less consistently included in the database, less likely to be accessible online, and less easy to quantify or compare between languages. We therefore have focused primarily on just two kinds of texts: corpora of annotated recordings, and Bible translations. Annotated multimedia corpora deposited in secure archives are the gold standard of language documentation. Bible translations are culturally important texts that are often the foundation of community literacy in Vanuatu's Indigenous languages.

Table 1 presents the different genres of language work we discuss in this article. We distinguish subcategories for four of these genres. For the category of other linguistic research, we calculated a research score which is roughly equivalent to the number of journal articles published about a language. The methodologies for categorisation, subcategorisation, and scoring are explained in detail in the relevant sections. This approach allows us to cover the Boasian trilogy (Evans & Dench, 2006; Woodbury, 2011) of reference grammar, lexicon, and collection of texts in some detail, while also considering other kinds of linguistic research and language work.

Table 1. Categories and subcategories of works related to Vanuatu languages discussed in this paper

Category	Subcategories or quantification	Section
Grammatical descriptions	Grammar Long grammar sketch Short grammar sketch	3
Lexical descriptions	Dictionary Long wordlist Short wordlist	4
Other linguistic research	Research score	5
Annotated multimedia corpora	Interlinearisation Translation (and transcription) Transcription only	6.1
Bible translations	Full Bible translation New Testament translation with audio New Testament translation Translation of parts of Bible In-progress translation	6.2

Categorising Vanuatu's Oceanic languages is not a straightforward task. There have been many attempts to list Vanuatu's languages at different points in time (e.g. Lynch & Crowley, 2001; Tryon, 2010; François et al., 2015). These lists differ for various reasons, including data availability, decisions about how to distinguish languages and dialects, and whether extinct and dormant languages are included. For practical purposes, we have chosen to follow the list of languages in Glottolog. Glottolog's listing is an attempt to reconcile previous works, and is continually updateable in response to new evidence (Forkel & Hammarström, 2022). Our list of 118 languages with Glottocodes appears in the summary table in the Appendix, and in a separate dataset in the supplementary material, which contains language names in Glottolog, but also alternative language names, and names of dialects that fall under a language-level Glottocode.⁵

It is important to note that Glottolog lists some dialects of Vanuatu languages with their own Glottocode. References inherited from Glottolog with a dialect Glottocode have been included under their parent language Glottocode in the discussion that follows, so that

⁵ In the dataset the `language_name` column shows the name we believe is most appropriate based on recent publications, which are most likely to reflect the speaker communities' current preferences. In this paper, we use these names when we mention specific languages, rather than the default language name in Glottolog, which is also available in the `glottolog_language_name` column in that dataset. Alternative names from other major sources are also included in separate columns. In the VanBib database, we also include a column showing the language name used in the source itself (`language_name_source`), to acknowledge that identification of languages changes over time and may reflect different varieties. We have not been able to confirm this for all entries imported from other datasets however, so this may default to the Glottolog language name. More details can be found in the documentation in the supplementary materials on Zenodo.

references related to all dialects of a language are discoverable.⁶ However, we understand that, in some cases, this choice can be problematic. For some languages, there is a tradition to study different dialects separately, and sometimes arguments for considering the varieties to be separate languages. Some examples are: the Uripiv-Atchin-Wala-Rano language (a.k.a. Northeast Malekula, Glottocode: urip1239); Malua-Tepërav (Glottocode: malu1245) with its dialects Espiegle's Bay and Malua Bay; and the Sakao-Nkep language of northeastern Santo (known collectively as Wanohe in Glottolog, Glottocode: saka1289). Considering the manageable number of works for such languages, it should be straightforward to determine any differences in inter-dialectal research coverage in such cases. We believe that our choices regarding language listing do not substantially affect our ability to identify areal and temporal patterns in language research in Vanuatu, and will allow linguists and community members to find relevant resources.

Another limitation of our methodology is that the VanBib database is by no means a complete listing of *every* work related to Vanuatu languages. Lynch and Crowley (2001, p. xii) acknowledge that much information about Vanuatu languages is unpublished and not carefully archived, “subject to the vagaries of cyclonic devastation, fire, flood, or even cockroaches and mould.” This problem continues despite efforts to archive and digitise many materials and the introduction of archiving and publication requirements by funding and academic institutions, as well as public institutions like the Vanuatu Cultural Centre. Major efforts have been made to digitise and archive resources for Vanuatu languages in the PARADISEC archive (Thieberger, 2023a). A project funded by the Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology is digitising works related to Vanuatu languages in the archives of the Society of Mary (Zamponi, Walworth & Rangelov, in prep). Another project is under way to document works at the Australian National Library with a grant from the same library to Prof. Matthew Spriggs (Spriggs, 2025).⁷ In the research category, there is much work that may be in progress or never published, but has been presented at conferences, or exists as drafts. Some such unpublished works were added to VanBib following a public call to colleagues working on Vanuatu languages, but many are not listed yet.

Another limitation is that despite our best efforts there are undoubtedly some errors in the coding in the VanBib database. In some cases, we have not been able to access the original sources to verify all facts, and we have had to code based on proxies. Some other limitations related to the specific categories are discussed in the respective sections.

Despite these limitations, we believe that the current state of the database provides solid ground for answering the research questions of this paper. We are most confident about the coverage of the most important and extensive works, such as reference grammars, dictionaries, research monographs, large annotated archived multimedia corpora, and complete Bible translations.

3 Grammatical Descriptions

In this section we will discuss grammatical descriptions of Vanuatu's Oceanic languages. We are restricting our definition of grammatical descriptions to reference works and

⁶ In the VanBib database, both the language code and the dialect code are retained.

⁷ <https://www.library.gov.au/news-media/announcing-recipients-2025-national-library-australia-fellowships-scholarships-and-0>

sketches that aim to cover at least the phonology, morphology and syntax of a language. Descriptions of just the phonology, or of specific grammatical features are covered in §5.

We have categorised these works into three groups, using length as an approximate measure of the detail and depth of grammatical description. Table 2 shows the length in pages for each of our three categories: full grammar, long grammar sketch, and short grammar sketch.

Table 2. Criteria for levels of grammatical description

Level of grammatical description	Length
Full grammar	More than 250 pages
Long grammar sketch	101-250 pages
Short grammar sketch	Up to 100 pages

The cut-off points are necessarily arbitrary, but are based on our observations regarding the amount of detail that can be covered in various sizes of works. For example, PhD theses that constitute a reference grammar would normally fit into the full grammar category, while descriptive grammars in Masters theses tend to be the length of a long grammar sketch. On the other hand, PhD theses that primarily address a specific topic in an under-researched language often also contain a grammar sketch of the language, which usually falls within the short or long grammar sketch category. In the case of monographs that include a grammatical description and a lexicon (e.g. Crowley, 1998, 2006a, 2006b, 2006c, 2006d), we have counted here only the length of the grammatical description, while the lexicon is treated separately in section 4. It should also be kept in mind that many short grammar sketches, especially those authored in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, do not follow modern grammaticography standards.

In our database, we find a total of 172 works that contain grammatical descriptions, including 27 full grammars, 24 long grammar sketches and 121 short grammar sketches.⁸ Many of these works describe the same languages, or reproduce description and examples from previous studies, for example in earlier works by Daniel MacDonald, Sidney Ray, and Robert Codrington, as well as in more recent works such as the grammar summaries in Lynch, Ross & Crowley (2002). Short grammar sketches may form the foundation for longer grammatical descriptions.

To give a better idea of the coverage across Vanuatu languages, Table 3 shows the number and percentage of Vanuatu languages that have been best described at each level of grammatical description. The highest level of grammatical description for each language is included in the summary table in the Appendix, and bibliographical details for all grammatical descriptions are available in the full dataset and the interactive map in the supplementary materials.

⁸ These totals (and Figure 4 in §3.2) exclude duplicates of grammars that were first available as a thesis, and then published as monographs with modification and additions. There are 14 examples like this in the database, see the R notebook in the supplementary materials for details.

Table 3. Level of grammatical description for Vanuatu languages

Highest level of grammatical description	Number of languages	Percentage of languages
Full grammar	27	22.9%
Long grammar sketch	20	16.9%
Short grammar sketch	28	23.7%
No grammatical description	43	36.4%

3.1 Across Vanuatu

The level of grammatical description available for each language is presented geographically in the maps in Figures 1-3. Each language is represented with a numbered circle positioned at the coordinates provided in Glottolog, shaded to reflect the highest level of grammatical description available. The index numbers are included in the summary table in the Appendix. To ensure that individual languages are always visible, even in dense linguistic areas like Malekula and Santo, we have split the maps into three regions: the northern region covers Torba, Sanma and Penama provinces (except South Pentecost); the central region covers Malampa and Shefa provinces, as well as South Pentecost; and the southern region covers Tafea province. This division also coincides with the Northern, Central, and Southern groups in which all of Vanuatu's non-Polynesian Oceanic languages have been argued to fall (Clark, 2009; Tryon, 2010). Alternatively, an interactive map for the whole of Vanuatu is included in the supplementary materials, which also provides bibliographical details for all grammatical descriptions associated with the language.

Figure 1. Map showing level of grammatical description for languages in Northern Vanuatu⁹

⁹ Details of specific packages used to generate maps and figures are included in the R html notebook in the supplementary materials.

Figure 2. Map showing level of grammatical description for languages in Central Vanuatu

Figure 3. Map showing level of grammatical description for languages in Southern Vanuatu

The geographic distribution shows Santo to be the most under-described area for grammatical features. There are five full grammars for languages along the eastern and southern coast of Santo, but most of the mainland, especially the language-dense mountainous western half, is poorly covered.

Malekula, the other large island with tens of languages, is much better covered than Santo. This is likely due to the groundbreaking work of Terry Crowley who started working on Malekula languages around the turn of the millennium and whose enthusiasm undoubtedly inspired many linguists to undertake work on Malekula. Notably, many descriptions of Malekula languages were produced at the University of Waikato in New Zealand, where Crowley was based from 1991. Two full grammars and ten sketches of Malekula languages have so far been produced at this institution, by Crowley himself and later through the Malekula Languages Project headed by Julie Barbour.

The rest of Malampa, Penama and Shefa have fairly uneven coverage, with a roughly even split between languages that have full grammars, long and short grammar sketches, or no grammatical descriptions at all, without strong intra-regional patterns. For many of the languages that do not have any grammatical description included in the database, we are aware of linguists producing other genres of descriptive research, which will be discussed in §5.

The most northerly and southerly provinces, Torba and Tafea, are relatively well covered in breadth, but not in as much depth. Although there is at least some grammatical description for almost all languages in Tafea, few of these are long enough to count as full grammars in our categorisation. However these include some of the earliest grammatical

descriptions of Vanuatu languages that follow modern standards of grammaticography, especially John Lynch's early work on Tanna languages.

3.2 Over time

Figure 4 shows how many grammatical descriptions of different lengths have been produced in every five-year period since 1956.¹⁰ All grammatical descriptions published before this were short grammar sketches, and there are 66 published between 1877 and 1955 in the dataset. The growth in the number and length of grammatical descriptions published since 1955 reflects the growing status and conventionalisation of descriptive grammars as a genre of linguistic research over this time period (cf. Ameka, Dench & Evans, 2006; Nakayama & Rice, 2014; Camp et al., 2018).

Figure 4. Grammatical descriptions of Vanuatu languages since 1956

Figure 4 shows that there have been two major pulses in grammatical description of Vanuatu languages. The first one was between 1971 and 1985, when John Lynch published a number of grammar sketches on Tafea languages, while Ross Clark, Jean-Michel Charpentier, Arthur Capell and others published grammar sketches on languages further north. During this period the first full grammar for a Vanuatu language appeared, Terry Crowley's grammar of Paama, released first as his PhD thesis in 1979 and published as a monograph in 1982.

¹⁰ Equivalent charts for all year ranges can be found in the R notebook in the supplementary materials.

The second, stronger impulse started in the 1990s. Since then, 25 full grammars and many grammar sketches have been published, as the number of linguists working on Vanuatu languages increased sharply, including many research students. During this period, the first grammars by ni-Vanuatu linguists, Hannah Vari-Bogiri (2011) and Lana Takau (2016, 2023) appeared. This pulse was also fuelled by growing calls for language documentation and description internationally (e.g. Himmelmann, 1998), better funding availability (e.g. ELDP grants since the 2000s), and technological progress, which made fieldwork and data collection easier. The peak in short grammar sketches between 2001 and 2005 reflects the collection of grammar sketches in Lynch, Ross & Crowley (2002). Most of these sketches were based on previously published work, but also encouraged further research on these and other Vanuatu languages in the following years.

The dip between 1985 and 1995 probably reflects the moratorium on foreign research from 1985 to 1994, and the subsequent rise has been fed by, among other things, the collaborative approach to research that was prioritised when the moratorium was lifted (Taylor & Thieberger, 2011, pp. xxvii–xxviii). There has been an apparent drop in grammaticography efforts since the mid 2010s, which is a worrying trend. This may be due to a range of factors including lower funding availability, the policy of some universities not to accept grammatical descriptions as PhD dissertations, and reduced training activities at USP's Emalus campus Pacific Languages Unit. The especially low count for the period 2021-2025 is probably partly due to COVID-19, which paused fieldwork efforts. Its effects will probably continue as the data collection, annotation and description process takes many years.

4 Lexical Descriptions

For works that constitute lexical descriptions, we distinguish between dictionaries and wordlists. Works we categorise as dictionaries offer more than a gloss in one or more other languages. They usually provide more detailed definitions, grammatical information and examples, and sometimes multimedia (audio and/or images). Dictionaries usually have several thousand entries. Wordlists lack much detail other than glosses, usually in English, French and/or Bislama.

We distinguish between short wordlists with up to 500 entries, and long wordlists with more than 500 entries. Short wordlists are limited to basic general vocabulary (Swadesh-list type, cf. List, 2018) and some culturally relevant frequent vocabulary items, or lists of words in a specific semantic domain (e.g. plant names). Long wordlists document many semantic domains including synonyms and finer semantic distinctions. The cut-off point of 500 items is somewhat arbitrary, but informed by Dockum & Bown's (2019) finding that a wordlist of at least 400 items is minimally sufficient in order to draw phonological generalisations about a language. Table 4 summarises the criteria for our categories.

Table 4: Criteria for levels of lexical description

Level of lexical description	Type of information	Number of entries
Dictionary	Details beyond glosses, such as definitions, word class information, examples.	More than 500
Long wordlist	Glosses only	More than 500
Short wordlist	Glosses only	Up to 500

There are 1308 individual word lists and dictionaries listed in our database for the 118 Oceanic languages of Vanuatu with Glottocodes. The vast majority are short wordlists (1220), 46 are long wordlists, and 42 are dictionaries.¹¹ Many of the short wordlists are curated from previously published wordlists, in some cases adding new information, such as reconstructions and cognate coding.

More so than grammatical description or other areas of linguistic research, lexical description in the form of wordlists lends itself to large multilingual projects. Collecting wordlists is a relatively quick way to gather linguistic data, and it is improved by but does not absolutely require long-term engagement with language communities. Progress of lexical description of Vanuatu languages has therefore been accelerated by large multilingual projects based on translation of lists of basic vocabulary items, or elicitation of targeted semantic fields (especially relating to traditional ecological knowledge).

Table 5 lists publications and databases which contain short or long wordlists for five or more Vanuatu languages. The projects are arranged in chronological order of publication, with a brief description of the genre of wordlists and any regional specialisation. The number of languages given here follows Glottolog's categorisation; some projects contain wordlists for multiple varieties that are categorised as a single language here. Together these projects account for 1127 of the wordlists in the database.

¹¹We are aware that the database is missing some lexical descriptions, including long wordlists and dictionaries, that are in circulation in language communities or available upon request from linguists. Technological developments, including lexicon and corpus management tools like Toolbox and FLEx (Fieldworks, 2024), and increased use of technology by speaker communities, make it increasingly easy for linguists to share draft descriptions via soft copies of documents, databases, websites, or apps. Thieberger's (2021) Nafsan dictionary is an example of a published dictionary that is also available as an app (<https://nthieberger.net/nafsandictapp.html>).

Table 5. Wordlist publications covering more than five languages

Publication	Description	Number of languages
<i>New Hebrides languages: An internal classification</i> (Tryon, 1976)	This seminal work offers 179 short wordlists (of up to 300+ entries, mostly basic vocabulary) for varieties covering the entire country.	109
<i>Some common trees of the New Hebrides and their vernacular names</i> (Gowers, 1976)	Tree names in various Vanuatu languages	34
<i>Atlas linguistique du Sud-Malakula / Linguistic atlas of South Malakula (Vanuatu)</i> . (Charpentier, 1982)	This linguistic atlas of South Malekula offers long wordlists (up to approx. 2000 entries) for 19 varieties spoken in the southern half of Malekula, with glosses in English, French and Bislama.	17
<i>Introduction a la végétation, a la flore et aux noms vernaculaires de l'île de Pentecôte (Vanuatu)</i> (Cabalion & Morat, 1983)	Plant names in Pentecost languages	5
<i>Kavas of Vanuatu. Cultivars of Piper Methysticum Forst.</i> (Lebot & Cabalion, 1988)	List of a handful of kava terms in languages across Vanuatu	29
<i>A guide to the common trees of Vanuatu with lists of their traditional uses and ni-Vanuatu names</i> (Wheatley, 1992)	Lists of tree names in languages across Vanuatu	35
<i>Comparative Austronesian Dictionary</i> (Tryon, 1995)	Long wordlists for seven Vanuatu languages	7
<i>Nem blong olkaen kakae: Repot blong sovei long Santo</i> (Walter et al., 1998)	Lists words for food items in languages throughout Santo.	29

Publication	Description	Number of languages
<i>Kokonas mo taros blong Vanuatu: Nem mo storian</i> (Caillon & Olfilwoka blong Kultural Senta, 2004)	Lists words for types of coconuts and taro in languages across Vanuatu.	34
<i>The Austronesian Basic Vocabulary Database (ABVD)</i> (Greenhill, Blust & Gray, 2008/2022)	This large database contains 392 basic vocabulary lists (up to 210 items), with cognate coding, for nearly all languages of Vanuatu including multiple varieties for some languages, collected over many years from published works and contributed directly by linguists working in Vanuatu. The latest Vanuatu lists were added in 2022.	114
<i>*Leo Tuai: A comparative lexical study of North and Central Vanuatu languages</i> (Clark, 2009)	Comparative dictionary including words from North-Central Vanuatu languages, and corresponding Proto North-Central Vanuatu reconstructions	15
<i>Austronesian Comparative Dictionary</i> (Blust, Trussel & Smith, 2010/2023)	Short wordlists with matching protolanguage reconstructions for 99 varieties from Vanuatu	82
<i>The Automated Similarity Judgment Program (ASJP) database</i> (Wichmann et al., 2022)	A list of up to 40 words for most Vanuatu languages, mostly extracted from Tryon (1976)	108
<i>Vanuatu Voices</i> (Takau et al., 2025)	A database of 234 short wordlists (up to 300+ entries) with audio recordings, IPA transcriptions, and glosses in Bislama and English. It currently covers varieties spoken on Malekula, Maewo, Ambae, Pentecost, Epi, the Shepherd Islands, and Santo, with work in progress on more Santo varieties.	56

Thanks in large part to ambitious projects like these, at least a short wordlist exists for all of the Vanuatu languages listed in Glottolog. However, this should not be taken as too much cause for celebration, as some languages identified in other sources are excluded from Glottolog (such as the additional 20 listed in François et al., 2015) due to lack of linguistic evidence to support analysis as separate languages. Of the 234 wordlists in *Vanuatu Voices*, 21 lists for Malekula and Santo languages cannot be associated with a language-level Glottocode with confidence. These may be additional wordlists for languages that already

exist in the database, or they could provide evidence for adding new languages to Glottolog (cf. Rangelov, 2025). Vanuatu Voices also includes two wordlists for Bislama.

Unlike short wordlists, dictionaries represent a significant investment of time and community organising. With a few exceptions, published dictionaries are usually only available for languages that have been the focus of sustained attention from linguists over many years or decades.

Unsurprisingly, there is overlap in the data published in different lexical descriptions. Many of the wordlist projects use data from Tryon's 1976 survey, which achieved remarkable coverage of Vanuatu's languages. To the best of our knowledge, and taking into account subsequent reflections in Tryon (2010), we believe that Tryon (1976) contains wordlists on 109 of the 118 Vanuatu languages listed in Glottolog. Similarly, languages that have been studied over a long period of time might have updated editions of dictionaries available, such as the dictionaries of Nafsan (Thieberger, 2011; Thieberger & Members of the Erakor community, 2021).

To show coverage across Vanuatu languages, Table 6 displays the number and percentage of Vanuatu languages according to the most detailed available lexical description. The highest level of lexical description for each language is given in the summary table in the appendix, and a list of all lexical descriptions for each language can be found in the interactive map or full database in the supplementary material.

Table 6. Level of lexical description for Vanuatu languages

Highest level of lexicon description	Number of languages	Percentage of languages
Dictionary	31	26.3%
Long wordlist	26	22.0%
Short wordlist	61	51.7%

4.1 Across Vanuatu

The maps in Figures 5-7 show the highest level of lexical description for languages of Northern, Central and Southern regions of Vanuatu, following the same boundaries as used for Figures 1-3, explained in section 3.1. The interactive map included in the supplementary materials provides a view of the same information across the whole of Vanuatu, and includes bibliographical details for all lexical descriptions in the dataset relevant to each language.

Figure 6. Map showing the highest level of lexical description for languages in Central Vanuatu

Figure 7. Map showing the highest level of lexical description for languages in Southern Vanuatu

The geographic distribution shows that, from a lexicography point of view, Santo is by far the least well studied area with only three dictionaries and two long wordlists for the 29 Santo languages in the database. Malekula would have been in a similar situation were it not for Charpentier's (1982) major work on South Malekula languages, as well as Crowley's later work.

Pentecost and Ambrym stand out as islands with excellent coverage for lexical description, as all but one language on each island has a published dictionary, and Apma of Central Pentecost has three dictionaries available. This coverage is the result of both early work by missionaries, internationally-funded multilingual projects in West Ambrym and North Pentecost, and collaboration between individual linguists and community members like Andrew Gray with Isaiah Tabi and Pascal Temwakon in Pentecost, and Mike Franjeh with communities in Northern Ambrym.

Languages of Tafea province and Efate Island also have many dictionaries or at least long wordlists, while those of Maewo, Ambae, Epi, and the Shepherd Islands, are less well described. In Torba province there are dictionaries for three of the 14 languages spoken there.

4.2 *Over time*

In this section, we will distinguish lexical descriptions gathered through the large multilingual projects described in Table 5 from other lexical descriptions. Figure 8 shows lexicographical developments since 1956. The bar chart in the upper part of the figure shows how many lexical descriptions outside of large projects have been produced per five-year

period. These projects focusing on individual languages are more easily compared with the progress of grammatical descriptions shown in Figure 4. The bottom part of the figure shows when the large multilingual projects in Table 5 were published on the same timeline (though some have continued to be updated).

Figure 8. Lexical descriptions of Vanuatu languages since 1956. Individual projects appear in the barplot on top; large multilingual projects are plotted on the timeline at the bottom.

Until 2006, there was a steady trickle of Vanuatu language dictionaries, with roughly one or two dictionaries published every five years since 1966. In the last twenty years this has increased to 5-8 dictionaries published every five years. Comparing Figure 8 with Figure 4, it seems that this marked increase in production of dictionaries is lagging behind production of reference grammars, which peaked in 2006-2010. Often language documentation and description projects first produce a grammar followed subsequently by a dictionary, such as von Prince's (2012/2015, 2017) grammar and dictionary of Daakaka, and Malau's (2016, 2021) grammar and dictionary of Vurës. The current surge in dictionary making may therefore subside like the peak in grammars, or face a delayed dip representing the disruption of the pandemic.

More optimistically, the increase in dictionaries over the last fifteen years may reflect the growing availability of a range of technical tools for managing lexicographical data and preparing dictionaries in different formats, including websites and apps. Greater ease in producing, publishing and updating dictionaries may encourage more linguists to mobilise lexical databases, and many are already informally sharing these formats with community members in ways that are not reflected in our database.

The different scale, goals and trajectories of large multilingual lexicon projects over time warrant a separate discussion here. Tryon's (1976) survey formed the foundation for lexical study of Vanuatu languages, and was by far the largest of these projects until the mid 2000s. Charpentier's (1982) lexical atlas of South Malekula provides massive amounts of primary data with long wordlists that were presented on maps. Subsequent twentieth century wordlist projects with primary data tended to have more specific regional or semantic scope.

Twenty-first century projects have been spurred by new possibilities for storing, organising and sharing lexical data. The *Austronesian Basic Vocabulary Database* (Greenhill, Blust & Gray, 2008) contains a total of 392 wordlists for Vanuatu languages with cognate coding, and includes many earlier wordlists, including parts of Tryon's, making them accessible online for a wider audience and in formats that enabled further analysis for reconstruction and other purposes. The *Vanuatu Voices* database's 234 short wordlists (Takau et al., 2025) contain primary data with audio recordings and IPA transcriptions, employing contemporary geographical mapping technology, which makes it easy to explore for both researchers and community members.

5 Other Linguistic Research

So far we have covered well-defined genres of research in descriptive linguistics, but we also hope to reflect the diversity of linguistic research on Vanuatu languages beyond grammars, grammar sketches, dictionaries, and wordlists. This section discusses other kinds of linguistic research on Vanuatu's Oceanic languages, **excluding** the source types covered in section 3 on grammatical description, and section 4 on lexical description. It also does not cover documentation corpora or other types of texts produced in Vanuatu languages, which we discuss in section 6. The comparisons and trends discussed in this section are necessarily more tentative than those in the previous sections. This is partly because we are less confident that our coverage of these other kinds of research in the database is complete, as it may disproportionately represent the work and interests of those who contributed to VanBib. A more epistemological reason for caution is that we are not comparing like with like within this more diverse genre of research. Our choices about how to categorise and quantify different kinds of linguistic research are necessarily approximate and somewhat arbitrary.

In this section we have included sources about phonology, comparative linguistics, dialectology, sociolinguistics, and other specific language features. These topic labels are categories used in Glottolog, which we have extended to other sources in the database. The specific feature category is a miscellaneous category which includes descriptions of features across all areas of linguistics. One category we have not included in this section is ‘ethnographic’, as these text types often do not discuss language specifically, and mostly consist of early European accounts of Vanuatu communities. In total there are 281 unique references in these categories in the database, of which 241 were categorised as being about a specific feature.

As well as topic, the database also includes information about the format of the research output, for example whether it is an article, presentation or book. As these types of research output can be of very different length and scope, we decided to assign a value to each type of research output, to calculate a ‘research score’ for each language. The research score takes a journal article as the most typical unit of research, and attempts to approximate how many journal articles the total research about a particular language is equivalent to (excluding grammatical and lexical description). We have therefore applied a multiplier to theses and books to show the greater amount of work these tend to represent. Conversely, we have equated a presentation to roughly half an article or chapter, as these tend to be less accessible and represent an earlier stage of research. Table 7 shows the score we have assigned to each type of research output.

Table 7. Research score assigned to different types of research output

Type of research output	Research score
Book, PhD thesis	3
Master’s thesis	2
Article, chapter	1
Presentation, conference presentation	0.5

A limitation of this method is that the relative significance of research outputs is not only determined by their type and size. While some works are dedicated to one language and discuss it in detail, including a lot of primary data, in others, the language of interest may be only one of many languages discussed. However, it is difficult to justify or implement a boundary between research where a particular language is the primary focus, or only of secondary interest. In the case of languages that have received very little attention, it is useful to be as inclusive as possible so that the database can help linguists and community members find all available linguistic research, even when it is very limited.

We are also aware that the database does not provide an exhaustive list of research publications on Vanuatu languages. We know that references to presentations that have not (yet) been published are missing for many languages. Overview articles that cover a wide range of languages are not consistently included under every relevant language code. Nevertheless, we are confident that the current state of the database provides enough data to allow us to make broad generalisations about the state of linguistic research on Vanuatu languages.

The mean research score per language is 5.8, though the median is lower at only 3, and 28 languages have a research score of 0, so nearly a quarter of Vanuatu languages have no research outputs of these types. More than a third of the languages (50) have a research score of two or less. This shows that a large proportion of Vanuatu languages have received very little attention in descriptive linguistic research other than wordlists or sketch grammars.

On the other hand, several languages are much better researched than the average. The 15 languages with the highest research scores (scoring 15 and above) are shown in Table 8. Research scores for all languages are included in the summary table in the Appendix. Please note that these research scores do not include grammatical and lexical descriptions, and should be considered alongside the ratings assigned in other sections of this article.

Table 8. Languages with highest research scores

Rank	Language	Glottocode	Research score	Region
1	Raga	hano1246	39	Penama
2	Mwotlap	motl1237	33	Torba
3	Vatlongos	sout2859	23	Ambrym-Paama
4	Mota	mota1237	21	Torba
5	Lewo	lewo1242	19	Shefa
5	Vurës	vure1239	19	Torba
7	Aneityum	anei1239	18	Tafea
7	Hiw	hiww1237	18	Torba
9	Lo-Toga	loto1240	17	Torba
10	Apma	apma1240	16.5	Penama
10	Whitesands	whit1269	16.5	Tafea
12	Paama	paam1238	16	AmbrymPaama
13	Nakanamanga	nort2836	15	Shefa
13	Sye	siee1239	15	Tafea
13	Vera'a	vera1241	15	Torba

In most cases, these relatively well-researched languages are those that have enjoyed sustained attention from linguists over a period of many decades. The top three languages demonstrate the diverse ways this research can accumulate. Raga is the most researched language, with publications spanning nearly 150 years, between 1879 and the current year (2025). The database includes research outputs about Raga from 11 different linguists, including three ni-Vanuatu linguists: Hannah Vari-Bogiri, Lana Takau and Jim Gure.

The second-most researched language is Mwotlap. Like Raga, the first research conducted on Mwotlap dates from the early period of missionary linguistics in Vanuatu, being described in Robert Codrington's *The Melanesian Languages* in 1885. But unlike Raga, Mwotlap's high research score of 33 largely reflects the continued efforts of a single linguist, Alexandre François, over a period of more than twenty-five years; François has discussed Mwotlap both in works dedicated to that language, and in a number of works on Northern Vanuatu languages as a group.

There is a large gap between the top two and the rest of the 15 most-researched languages, which are more closely-spaced with research scores between 15 and 23. Like

Raga, most of these languages have been researched by many linguists over a number of decades, and many have been key languages in the research of Terry Crowley and John Lynch. Vatlongos is an interesting case, having the third highest score despite limited grammatical description. Gary J. Parker's dictionary and three articles published between 1968 and 1970 proved a solid foundation for Vatlongos to be included in subsequent comparative research on Vanuatu languages, including by John Lynch and Terry Crowley, who also conducted supplementary primary research with informants in Port Vila. In more recent years primary research has been conducted by Eleanor Ridge and Mike Franjeh. Vatlongos's high score on this metric shows the cumulative impact of sustained research over time involving multiple researchers.

5.1 Across Vanuatu

Figures 10-12 present the research score for languages in maps of North, Central and Southern Vanuatu, with more intense colours reflecting higher research scores. The interactive map in the supplementary materials shows the same information across Vanuatu, and includes the bibliographical details for all the research outputs used to calculate the research score for each language.

Figure 10. Map showing research score for languages in Northern Vanuatu

Figure 11. Map showing research score for languages in Central Vanuatu

Figure 12. Map showing research score for languages in Southern Vanuatu

In line with the regional patterns for grammatical and lexical description, the languages of Santo are the least well-researched regional group by this metric, followed by Malekula languages. Languages of Torba have consistently high research scores, and languages of Tafea are also fairly well covered with middle to high research scores. Many languages of Shefa, Ambrym and Paama have good research scores, though the coverage is patchier than in Torba or Tafea. Aside from Raga and Apma, languages of Penama have very few research outputs of this type, even though they have relatively high levels of grammatical description, and most Pentecost languages have a dictionary.

Perhaps because this measure is more gradated, regional patterns are more consistent and easily observed for research scores than for levels of grammatical and lexical description. It may be that regional social networks have a larger effect on these miscellaneous research outputs than on grammars and dictionaries which require more significant and sustained funding, resources and support.

5.2 Over time

Figure 13 displays the historical developments in research output for the past 70 years. To generate the figure, we used the research score of all relevant works in our database, sorted by year. Works that are tagged with more than one language were counted only once. Overall the chart shows consistent growth in linguistic research on Vanuatu languages over time.

Figure 13. Research score of linguistic research on Vanuatu languages published in five-year periods since 1956, other than grammatical and lexical descriptions

The results show that prior to 1965, research output was minimal, then it grew until the turn of the millennium which saw a steep increase in linguistic research on Vanuatu languages. This coincides with a period of increasing global recognition of the importance of including under-researched languages in linguistic research, and in the importance of documentation and description of endangered languages. Research output has experienced a more pronounced boost since the mid-2010s. This period stands out for the number of linguists, including many early career researchers, who published on Vanuatu languages.

The apparent fall in the 2021-2025 period in the graph is likely due to the fact that works to be published later in 2025 have not been included here. If only the articles in this special issue and its two companion issues were included, the 2021-2025 score would be higher than in 2016-2020. Additionally, some research presented at the well-attended 2023 Vanuatu Languages Conference in Port Vila and at the recent Conference on Oceanic Linguistics (COOL13) in Canberra, where about a third of the presentations had a Vanuatu language as a central topic, are also not included in the VanBib database and will hopefully be reflected in publications in the next few years. The score for 2021-2025 could perhaps also have been even higher were it not for the effects of COVID-19, which severely constrained data collection and put funding availability on pause for a couple of years, though perhaps this more flexible research genre was less affected than grammatical descriptions (see §3.2).

6 Texts, Recordings and Annotation

To complete the Boasian trilogy, in this section we aim to give a very broad overview of the availability of texts produced in the Oceanic languages of Vanuatu.

From a language documentation perspective, ‘texts’ usually refer to transcription of spoken language events, usually with further annotation like translation and morpheme-level glossing (interlinearisation). Technological developments from the end of the twentieth century onwards mean that audio or video recordings are also increasingly made available alongside the transcription, and annotations can be time-aligned to the recording to increase transparency, verifiability and richness. The goal of a collection of texts as part of a language documentation project is to provide a record of maximally naturalistic language use in its cultural setting, as well as data to support grammatical and lexical description. To address coverage of these kinds of text collections in Vanuatu’s Oceanic languages, we investigate annotated multimedia corpora deposited in secure archives, and compare the level of annotation available in section 6.1.

Written texts are also an important part of language development and planning, to support literacy in Indigenous languages and wider educational goals. Most of Vanuatu’s Oceanic languages do not have a long tradition of use in writing, and many do not have a consistent or linguistically informed orthography. Patterns of multilingual language use in Vanuatu favour the use of Bislama, English and French in domains where writing is most relevant, such as religious institutions, formal education, communication with authorities, and trade. Until fairly recently, colonial and post-colonial language policies have favoured this relegation of Vanuatu’s Oceanic languages to oral domains. Nevertheless, speakers of Vanuatu’s Oceanic languages do write texts in them every day, including in private and local domains, and increasingly in informal written domains such as text messaging and social media.

Languages that were used as *lingua francas* for early missionary work were the first to be written, and early missionaries developed writing systems with the aim of disseminating translations of religious texts such as prayers, hymns, catechisms and Bible passages (see Lindstrom, 2025, companion issue). More recent translation projects by the Summer Institute of Linguists (SIL) and other organisations have led to publication of many partial and complete Bible translations, the result of years of dedicated collaborative work with Vanuatu language communities. Due to the importance of Christianity for many ni-Vanuatu in different language communities and churches, the availability of Bible translations is a key factor in supporting community literacy in Vanuatu’s Indigenous languages. They are also a useful source of data for linguistic analysis. We therefore discuss the progress of these projects in section 6.2.

Other kinds of written texts and literacy materials are not as consistently covered in the VanBib database so we will not discuss them in detail in this section. However, we want to acknowledge how important the availability of accessible, interesting and culturally appropriate texts is to supporting literacy in Vanuatu’s Indigenous languages, which in turn supports language maintenance and wider educational goals. Missionaries, linguists and community members have produced a wide range of texts throughout the period covered in the database. We are aware that there are many more such texts which are not included in the database and may be difficult to access. Some may be hiding in libraries, analogue archives or private collections (see §2), others may be in use by local communities, but not available more widely, including for reasons related to the protection of local knowledge.

One of the most significant projects to produce texts in Vanuatu languages was the Ministry of Education and Training’s publication of translations of graded readers to support delivery of early years curriculum in Vanuatu’s Indigenous languages (Daly and Barbour, 2019; Early and Tamtam, 2015; Franjeh et al., 2025, companion issue; MOET, 2012). These texts can themselves be used as a corpus for a particular language (Barbour

and Williams, 2017) or source of parallel examples across languages (Gray, 2025, companion issue). Around the same period the Christensen Fund funded literacy materials in a number of Vanuatu languages, including North Ambrym, Nese and Ske. SIL's e-book platform Bloom¹² hosts literacy materials for a number of Vanuatu languages, including some produced through the Ministry of Education and Training's translation workshops.

Other language resources that may become increasingly important are digital resources necessary for natural language processing (NLP) applications, including adjusted dictionaries and morphological analysers, POS-tagged corpora, parallel corpora, and treebank collections. Many of the annotated corpora mentioned in the next section include POS-tagging, and sometimes an associated lexical database that could form the basis for the creation of NLP applications. Corpora in edited cross-linguistic collections stand out for the consistency and level of detail of their annotations, making them especially suitable for NLP purposes. Two Vanuatu languages are included in MultiCAST, following the GRAID and RefIND annotation schemes (Haig and Schnell, 2023). Five Vanuatu languages are represented in the DoReCo project (Seifart et al., 2024), which as well as standardised morphological annotations includes time-aligned annotations for individual segments supporting fine-grained phonetic analysis or modelling.

6.1 *Annotated audio and video corpora*

Annotated corpora of audio and video recordings are the gold standard in modern language documentation and description. They have a number of substantial advantages over written texts and translations. Firstly, they can be records of relatively natural speech acts, bearing in mind that the act of recording itself is an intervention in the communicative context. Secondly, they provide phonetic and prosodic detail, which is otherwise unavailable in written texts. Thirdly, video can provide recordings of gestures and other aspects of multimodal communication. All this is important for the communities of speakers because it allows them to have access to a much more comprehensive record of their language (see, however, François, 2018, pp. 283–284 for a discussion on challenges regarding accessibility). These resources also make it possible to create literacy, entertainment, and other materials, which can be distributed through modern channels of communication, including social media. This has the potential to improve the language's response to new domains – an important factor for a language's vitality, according to UNESCO's criteria (Brenzinger et al., 2003). Another factor for language vitality according to UNESCO is the amount and quality of documentation in itself. This is important for, among other things, better language description and understanding the structural and lexical patterns of languages. Modern linguistic research relies on annotated multimedia corpora to enable in-depth analysis, verifiability and replicability (Berez-Kroeker et al., 2017).

We reviewed all linguistic data archives that are members of the Digital Endangered Languages and Musics Archives Network (DELAMAN), and other well-known archives, for deposits of multimedia recordings of speech in Vanuatu languages with time-aligned annotations. We identified 71 collections for 46 languages in the following archives: ELAR¹³, PARADISEC (Thieberger and Barwick, 2012), Pangloss (Michailovsky et al., 2014; Adamou et al., 2025), DoBeS (Brugman et al., 2002), DoReCo (Seifart et al., 2024), Multi-CAST (Haig and Schnell, 2023) and The Language Archive.¹⁴

¹² <https://bloom.sil.org/home>

¹³ www.clararchive.org

¹⁴ <https://archive.mpi.nl/tla/>

We tagged each collection for one of three levels of annotation (from low to high): (1) transcription (where the speech is only transcribed in the language of the recording), (2) translation (where the transcribed speech is also translated into Bislama, English and/or French), (3) interlinearisation (where the transcribed text is broken down into morphemes with glosses). There were a few corpora of recordings with no annotation, but we did not include those in these statistics. While they are worth archiving and of potential use to community members, they are less accessible and searchable, and are difficult to distinguish from recordings made for other, non-linguistic purposes.

In most cases, collection descriptions or metadata do not provide statistics about how much of the content of a collection has been annotated to these different levels. We identified the level of annotation by manually checking a sample of bundles in each collection, and listing the highest level of annotation we could find. It is important to acknowledge that the corpora vary in relation to the amount of data, and the proportion that has been annotated according to the highest identified level. One corpus that stands out for its size, quality and annotation detail is Mike Franjeh's corpus on Northern Ambrym languages (Franjeh, 2018), which was awarded the 2019 DELAMAN award.¹⁵

Table 9 shows the number and percentage of Vanuatu's Oceanic languages which have an annotated corpus at different levels of annotation. The summary table in the Appendix shows the highest annotation level for each language. Just over a quarter of languages have a corpus that contain at least some texts with interlinear glossing. Just over a tenth have transcription and translation for at least some texts, and one language has transcription as the highest level of annotation. Nearly two thirds of languages do not have any annotated corpus available in these archives. The high proportion of languages with no annotated corpus makes it difficult to draw conclusions about the regional distribution of this kind of documentation, but the languages of Torba and Shefa provinces, and Pentecost and Ambrym appear to be best covered.

Table 9. Level of annotation for annotated multimedia corpora of Vanuatu languages

Highest level of annotation	Number of languages	Percentage of languages
Interlinearisation	32	27.1%
Translation	13	11.0%
Transcription	1	0.8%
No annotated corpus	72	61.0%

The data in these collections were collected in the past thirty years. They undoubtedly reflect a tradition of data collection and annotation driven by the increased interest in work on under-documented languages (see François, 2018, p. 280 for a discussion of this in the Pacific context), as well as technological developments, which made the recording, processing, annotation, and archiving of speech increasingly more manageable, particularly

¹⁵ <https://www.delaman.org/news/delaman-franz-boas-award-2019-awarded-to-michael-franjeh/>

in a field setting. During this period, many funding bodies, most notably ELDP, have made grants conditional on archiving data, further incentivising the deposit of annotated corpora.

6.2 Bible translations

Bible translations are long-term projects involving great commitment and collaboration between community members and outside experts. They are organised, coordinated and supervised by organisations with reputation and expertise such as SIL and the Bible Society of the South Pacific. Bible translations engage community members in the process, and the availability of scriptures in a language increases its prestige, improves speaker and institutional attitudes towards the language, and allows the language to expand to a new and important domain. These are also important factors for a language's vitality, according to UNESCO (Brenzinger et al., 2003). Bible translation projects result in texts of substantial size and consistent quality. They can therefore be a useful resource for linguistic research, including as parallel corpora (see Dahl, 2007; Mayer & Cysouw, 2014; Sjöberg, 2023).

In this section we rely on a summary of Bible translation projects in Vanuatu, kindly provided to us by Mike Bryant at SIL Vanuatu in March 2025, as well as other Bible translations listed in VanBib. Bible translation projects usually focus on the New Testament as the first major milestone, and for more recent projects this has also involved recording audio for audiobook and read-along editions to support literacy acquisition. A full Bible translation also includes the Old Testament. There are also translations of parts of the Bible listed in the VanBib database, though we are less confident about the coverage of these shorter translations especially in relation to community-led projects. These partial translations include older works by early missionaries that may now be difficult to access, or reflect earlier varieties of contemporary languages. We also report on ongoing Bible projects that have started recently.

Table 10 shows the number and percentage of languages by the highest level of Bible translation available, as well as whether a project is in progress for languages with no currently available translations. Information per language can be found in the summary table in the Appendix. There is a further in-progress Bible translation project for Ndiai, spoken in South-West Santo, which is likely a separate language but does not yet have a Glottocode. Furthermore, the available translations in six languages (Mota, Tamambo, Lelepa, Mele-Fila, Nafsan, Aneityum) are currently undergoing revisions and updates (Mike Bryant, pers. comm.).

Table 10. Progress of Bible translation for Vanuatu languages

Stage of Bible translation	Number of languages	Percentage of languages
Full Bible translation	4	3.4%
New Testament translation with audio ¹⁶	14	11.9%
New Testament translation (no audio)	6	5.1%
Translation of Bible parts	23	19.5%
Bible translation in progress	6	5.1%
No translation reported	65	55.1%

7 Bislama, English and French

In the preceding sections we have focused exclusively on the Oceanic languages of Vanuatu, those that are often referred to by the Bislama term *lanwis* in contrast to languages used on a national scale (Crowley, 2003; Ridge, 2025, this issue). Bislama, English and French were all introduced to Vanuatu through European colonisation of the archipelago and wider Pacific. The introduction of these new languages along with huge socioeconomic change favoured new hierarchical models of multilingualism (François, 2011). Bislama especially is used as a lingua franca for communication between ni-Vanuatu who do not speak mutually intelligible Oceanic varieties, while English and French became closely associated with prestigious domains of religion, education and interacting with colonial administrators. Unlike English and French, Bislama is also increasingly a first language and sometimes sole first language for an increasing proportion of Ni-Vanuatu, especially in urban areas (Lavender-Forsyth, 2025). According to the Constitution of the Republic of Vanuatu (Republic of Vanuatu, 1980/2006), Bislama, English, and French are the three official languages of the country. While Bislama has unique status as Vanuatu's national language, English and French are sometimes referred to as the languages of education.

7.1 Bislama

In our database there are 169 works relating to Bislama. While there are a few publications from the first half of the 20th century, work on Bislama picked up in the mid-1970s and then significantly after Independence, when Bislama became the national language of Vanuatu. In the preface to Crowley's (2004) grammar of Bislama, he describes how his initial view of Bislama as a tool to gain access to Vanuatu's Oceanic languages changed over time as he came to recognise Bislama as worthy of linguistic research in its own right. Growing interest in contact languages and Bislama's ambiguous status as a pidgin or creole language may also have encouraged linguists to take the study of Bislama more seriously over this time period.

There are a number of lexical and grammatical descriptions of Bislama. Terry Crowley's (2003) *A new Bislama dictionary*, published first in 1995 and then as a second

¹⁶ None of the full Bible translations have associated audio.

edition in 2003, stands out as the most detailed Bislama dictionary. Crowley's *Bislama reference grammar*, published in 2004 remains the most detailed reference grammar of Bislama. With its approximately 200 pages, this volume would count as a long grammar sketch according to our criteria, which means that Bislama's structure may be described in less detail than that of many of Vanuatu's less widely spoken Oceanic languages, at least in a single volume. Due to its status as a national lingua franca, there are also a number of grammatical reference works that have the primary aim of supporting language learners, rather than linguistic description in its own right.

On the other hand, Bislama has been the subject of far more linguistic research of other genres. With a research score of 118 in our scoring system described in section 5, linguistic research on Bislama far outweighs the most studied of Vanuatu's Oceanic languages, at more than three times the research score of Raga (Table 8). There are many works dedicated to Bislama's history, lexicon, and sociolinguistic variation – Terry Crowley and Miriam Meyerhoff being among the most prolific authors. Bislama's place in Vanuatu's educational system has also been discussed in detail by Robert Early, Helen Tamtam, Leslie Vandeputte and Fiona Willans, among others. This sociolinguistic focus is not surprising given Bislama's origins as a pidgin, its high variability, its use across a variety of domains, its geographic spread, and its complex relationship with the Oceanic languages that form its substrate.

Because of Bislama's status as a national language, many documents are produced in the language daily. We are aware of four dedicated curated corpora of Bislama text and/or recordings: The Meyerhoff Corpus of Bislama (Meyerhoff, 2000), the PLAIN corpus (Barth et al., 2020), a corpus which is being curated at ZAS in Berlin (Aru et al., 2024), and another one under creation at ANU in Canberra as part of the Modelling Pacific Creole Languages project (Thieberger, 2023b; Thieberger et al., 2025). Many of the corpora for Indigenous languages (§5) also contain translations into Bislama, as well as sociolinguistic surveys and interviews conducted in Bislama. There is also a full translation of the Bible in Bislama among a variety of other religious texts including hymn books.

In terms of digital resources and natural language processing applications, Bislama lags behind other national languages around the world. For example, widely used social media platforms or software packages provided by international corporations do not offer Bislama as an interface language, making it difficult to provide support like keyboards, captioning or translations. However, some of the popular large language models are able to respond to Bislama prompts and produce coherent text in Bislama, showing that it would be relatively easy for technology corporations to extend infrastructural support for Bislama. One of the goals of the Modelling Pacific Creole Languages project is to create resources that can be used to develop communication tools for Bislama and other Pacific Creoles. An English-to-Bislama machine translation tool is under construction by Raphaël Merx as part of this project (Thieberger et al., 2025).¹⁷

7.2 English and French

While the importance and equality of English and French are emphasised in national domains like education and politics, we know very little about the linguistics of English and French as used in Vanuatu. As far as we are aware, data and research related to the lexicon and structure of English and French as they are used in Vanuatu, as first or subsequent languages by various communities and in various domains, is very rare. One exception is

¹⁷ <https://bislama-trans.rapha.dev/translate/>

Green (2012), who explores variation in the use of English among USP students from different Pacific countries, including Vanuatu. Despite growing interest in World Englishes and studies of national varieties of coloniser languages elsewhere in the Pacific (e.g. Biewer, 2015), in Vanuatu we do not have sufficient data to even determine to what extent the local varieties of English and French are distinct or consistent enough to be distinguished from other varieties (see Schneider et al., 2025, companion issue).

There is somewhat more research into the sociolinguistics of English and French in Vanuatu, often with an applied focus. Lynch and Crowley (2001, pp. 28–29) list a few works that deal with English and French in Vanuatu, mostly focused on language policy, including educational policy. In recent years, more work on this topic has been published, especially following developments in Vanuatu’s policies regarding the languages of instruction in primary schools, including work by Robert Early and Fiona Willans. Schneider (2023) compares use of English with Bislama in legal settings. There are still many questions about the linguistic features and sociolinguistic practices associated with English and French in Vanuatu.

8 Summary and Discussion

We conclude by exploring how different types of language work discussed in this article relate to each other, summarising regional trends, and discussing the trajectory of linguistic research in Vanuatu.

8.1 *Types of research*

In this section we will look at how the different types of documentation, research and language work relate to each other for individual Vanuatu languages. The five types we have examined are: grammatical description, lexical description, other linguistic research, annotated corpora and Bible translations. The colour-coded summary table in the Appendix also helps to visualise the results for these types and the relationships between them. While there is an overall tendency for better researched languages to have better coverage across all types, there are also some surprising omissions, and patterns in the relationships between types.

Many languages with grammars do not have dictionaries: of the 27 languages with full grammars, only 11 also have a dictionary, while 10 have only short wordlists. On the other hand, most languages with dictionaries also have grammars or long grammar sketches (22 out of 31). Of the rest, 7 have only short grammar sketches and two have no grammatical description at all. These results probably reflect that traditionally many documentation projects prioritise grammatical description before lexical descriptions, so we may see more dictionaries being published for languages that have been described in full grammars in recent years.

The research score shows approximately how many journal articles or equivalent linguistic research on a language is available, excluding grammatical and lexical description that we have already discussed. Of the 31 languages with a relatively high research score (at least 10), nearly a third (9 languages) have no corpus in our database. However, there are Bible translations of at least the New Testament for 14 of these highly researched languages, which can also serve as corpora for linguistic analysis. Over half (17) of the 31 languages with a high research score also have a dictionary, while only 11 have a full grammar. The number of languages that have high research scores but no dictionary or full grammar likely reflect pressures on scholars to prioritise other kinds of research outputs,

due to funding availability and the demands of academic institutions. Languages with a low research score also tend to be poorly documented and researched. Of the 50 languages with a research score of 2 or less, only 4 have a dictionary, 4 have a full grammar, 6 have a corpus with some interlinearisation, and only 2 have Bible translations of at least the New Testament. This demonstrates the necessity of documentation and description to support other kinds of linguistic research.

Of the 32 languages for which there are interlinearised corpora in our database, there are full grammars for 15, and long grammar sketches for 9. Interlinearised corpora are usually created as part of projects that combine the documentation and description of a language, often following funding bodies' requirements. On the other hand, of the 13 languages with corpora featuring translation (but no interlinearisation) only two have a full grammar and none have a long grammar sketch. This is a good reminder of the interdependence of description of grammatical structures and consistent analysis of language data.

All 24 languages with an available translation of at least the New Testament of the Bible have some level of grammatical description, of which a third (8) are full grammars and a quarter (6) are long grammar sketches. More than half of these languages also have a dictionary (14). The languages that have both a Bible translation and detailed grammatical and lexical description tend to be larger languages, or languages spoken in areas that are less remote (in the sense of both current transport infrastructure and history of contact with colonisers), such as Raga, Paama, Nafsan and Sye.

8.2 Regional patterns

Drawing on the discussions in the rest of the paper and the summary table shown in the Appendix, this section will make some generalisations about the coverage of the different regions of Vanuatu, and research on the official languages.

Starting in the North, the 14 **Torba** languages stand out for their relatively high linguistic research scores due to the efforts of a number of linguists, including Alex François, Catriona Malau, and Stefan Schnell, since the turn of the millennium. However, there are only two full grammars, three dictionaries and one Bible translation for these languages. **Santo** is by far the least well covered part of Vanuatu by all measures. This is likely due to its size, geography, lack of infrastructure, and the sheer number of languages. Notable exceptions are a few languages along the more accessible eastern and southern coasts (Sakao-Nkep, Mavea, Tutuba, Tamambo and Araki). The discrepancy between these languages and the rest of Santo is substantial. A new and ongoing documentation project focused on Western Santo aims to address this gap (Rangelov, 2025; Taman, Taman, & Rangelov, 2025, this issue). **Maewo's** three languages score quite poorly, except for one full grammar. **Ambae's** languages stand out for their Bible translations and grammatical descriptions, but lag behind in the other categories.

Malekula, which is similar to Santo in terms of size and number of languages, is substantially better covered, not in the least due to work by Jean-Michel Charpentier and Terry Crowley, and traditions established by them, which paved the way for other researchers to engage with Malekula's languages. The least well covered area of Malekula is its central region. **Pentecost, Ambrym, Paama, Shepherds, and Efate** stand out as the best performing islands, which reflects many decades of linguistic work on their languages. In the case of Efate, its accessibility likely plays an important role. The language of Paama in particular stands out as one of the best performing languages of Vanuatu due to a

combination of Terry Crowley's work on it for many years, Bible translation efforts, and a contemporary multimedia corpus created by linguistic anthropologist Simon Devylder. Paama demonstrates that the best coverage is achieved by the efforts of different projects over many years. For **Epi**'s six languages there are two full grammars, two New Testament translations, and some research works, but they are mostly lagging behind in terms of lexical description and multimedia corpora.

The **Tafea** languages are relatively well covered in breadth but less so in depth regarding grammatical descriptions, i.e. most languages have some kind of grammatical description, but only one (Sye) has a full grammar. These languages have relatively good research scores and lexical descriptions, due to the consistent efforts of John Lynch and other linguists for the past at least five decades. Almost all of these languages have Bible translations, likely due to a long tradition of missionary activity and colonisation. Conversely, only Whitesands has an annotated linguistic corpus of the Tafea languages.

Of the official languages, Bislama is the best studied, and scores nearly three times as highly as the most researched Oceanic language of Vanuatu for general linguistic research. A more detailed reference grammar of Bislama is due, and work on accessible multimedia corpora is in progress. Regarding English and French, as used in Vanuatu, these are on par with the worst described languages of the country in terms of grammar, lexicon and corpora. Attitudes related to prescriptivism and underappreciation of the non-standard varieties spoken in Vanuatu are likely factors for this lack of attention, even if the global variation in these large world languages is increasingly well studied.

Many factors affect the coverage of an area. The number of speakers of a language is one factor. Of the largest languages of Vanuatu (see Lynch & Crowley, 2001, p. 6 for a list of the 13 languages with population over 5,000 at the time), most are relatively well covered, including Uripiv-Atchin-Wala-Rano, Raga, Apma, Paama, Nakanamanga, Nafsan, North Ambrym and most of Tanna's languages. Infrastructure and accessibility are important enabling factors, determining both how easy it is for outsider researchers to reach a speaker community and how likely it is for speakers of languages to access training or contact outside experts. Research traditions play a less tangible but important role in determining regional coverage. Once the ground is broken in a region, it becomes easier for work to continue. The difference in coverage between the two most linguistically diverse islands of Vanuatu, Santo and Malekula, can probably be attributed, at least in part, to stronger traditions of research in Malekula. From a community perspective, existing projects can prompt neighbouring communities to seek the support of outside experts. From a researcher perspective, research on a previously un(der)documented language often raises theoretical questions, which linguists may want to answer through comparisons with closely related languages. The lack of tradition for research on Vanuatu varieties of English and French is reflected in the limited research on the languages of education. Traditions of research are themselves informed by missionary and colonial histories of contact with outsiders.

8.3 *Developments over time*

In terms of historical developments in linguistic research in Vanuatu, our results first show an obvious major improvement of the state of affairs compared to Lynch and Crowley's (2001, p.15ff) estimate, where only four languages were ranked as well described (five stars), 12 languages as reasonably well described (four stars) and 11 languages as "middling" (three stars). Many works have been created since then, not least due to the traditions fostered by these two researchers, as well as technological advancements and

more diverse sources of funding. Research methodologies emphasizing collaborations with speaker communities, supported by both global developments and Vanuatu-specific efforts coordinated by the Vanuatu Cultural Centre, have also supported growth in research, and hopefully made research more meaningful and accessible to community members.

Our charts of historical developments (in sections 3.2, 4.2, 5.2) show a spike of activity since the 2000s. The effects of the COVID-19 pandemic have impacted outputs, especially grammaticography, both because fieldwork was impossible for many linguists, but also because funding availability was impacted. The pandemic's effects will likely continue to be felt at least in the next few years. The results of this paper highlight the need for continued work, identify gaps and trends that can help all stakeholders set their priorities, and hopefully inspire speakers of Vanuatu languages and ni-Vanuatu and outsider linguists to continue doing excellent work in this place of outstanding linguistic diversity.

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Supplementary Materials

The following supplementary materials accompany this article.

- The VanBib database: a dataset of references for resources about Vanuatu languages: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17628152> (version 1.3)
- A database of names for Vanuatu languages and lects: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17628402> (version 1.2)
- Interactive maps in html format showing the distribution of grammatical descriptions, lexical descriptions and research score for Vanuatu's Oceanic languages. Hover text for each language includes a list of bibliographical details for relevant resources. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17628367> (version v2)
- An R markdown notebook in html format showing code for generating overview statistics, maps and charts. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17628336> (version v2)

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Appendix: Summary Table

Region	Index	Language name	Glottocode	Grammar	Lexicon	Research score	Annotated corpus	Bible
Torba	1	Hiw	hiww1237	No grammar	Short list	18.0	Translation	Bible parts
	2	Lo-Toga	loto1240	Short sketch	Long list	17.0	Translation	Bible parts
	3	Lehali	leha1243	Short sketch	Short list	11.0	No corpus	No Bible
	4	Lehalurup	leha1244	Short sketch	Short list	11.0	No corpus	No Bible
	5	Mwotlap	motl1237	Full grammar	Dictionary	33.0	Translation	Bible parts
	6	Lemerig	leme1238	Short sketch	Short list	13.0	Translation	No Bible
	7	Mota	mota1237	Short sketch	Dictionary	21.0	Translation	Full Bible
	8	Vera'a	vera1241	Long sketch	Short list	15.0	Interlinear	Bible parts
	9	Vurës	vure1239	Full grammar	Dictionary	19.0	Interlinear	No Bible
	10	Nume	nume1241	Short sketch	Short list	8.0	Translation	No Bible
	11	Koro-Olrat	koro1308	No grammar	Short list	7.0	Translation	No Bible
	12	Lakon	lako1245	Short sketch	Short list	12.0	Translation	Bible parts
	13	Dorig	weta1242	No grammar	Short list	13.0	Translation	No Bible
	14	Merlav	merl1237	Short sketch	Short list	11.0	Translation	Bible parts
Samna	15	Valpei	valp1237	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	16	Vunapu	vuna1239	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	17	Tanokuk	noku1237	Short sketch	Short list	3.0	No corpus	Bible parts
	18	Pwelmau	piam1242	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	19	Sakao-Nkep	saka1289	Full grammar	Dictionary	7.0	Interlinear	Bible parts
	20	'Oa	tasm1246	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	21	Tolomako	tolo1255	Short sketch	Short list	0.0	No corpus	Bible parts
	22	Tiale	tial1239	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	In progress
	23	Ngen	shar1244	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	24	Tuijo-Kula	wusi1237	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	25	Merei	mere1242	Short sketch	Short list	4.0	No corpus	In progress
	26	Tie	navu1237	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	27	Nethalp	lore1244	No grammar	Short list	1.0	No corpus	No Bible
	28	Farafi	butm1237	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	29	Ande	moro1286	No grammar	Short list	2.0	No corpus	No Bible
	30	Mores	rori1237	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	31	Mavea	mafe1237	Full grammar	Short list	1.0	Interlinear	No Bible
	32	Kiai	fort1240	No grammar	Long list	3.0	No corpus	No Bible
	33	Polonombauk	polo1242	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	34	Tambotalo	tamb1253	No grammar	Short list	1.0	No corpus	No Bible
	35	Amblong	amb11237	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	36	Farsaf	nara1263	No grammar	Short list	1.0	No corpus	No Bible
	37	Tatangoa	tang1347	Short sketch	Dictionary	3.0	No corpus	NT with audio
	38	Ale	wail1242	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	39	Aore	aore1237	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	40	Tutuba	tutu1241	Full grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	41	Araki	arak1252	Full grammar	Dictionary	4.0	Interlinear	No Bible
	42	Akei	akei1237	Short sketch	Short list	0.0	No corpus	Bible parts
	43	Tamambo	malo1243	Full grammar	Long list	5.0	No corpus	New Testament
Penama	44	Sunwadia	mari1426	Full grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	Bible parts
	45	Central Maewo	cent2058	Short sketch	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	46	Baetora	baet1237	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	Bible parts
	47	East Ambae	east2443	Full grammar	Short list	4.0	No corpus	NT with audio
	48	West Ambae	west2513	Long sketch	Short list	0.0	No corpus	NT with audio
	49	Raga	hano1246	Full grammar	Dictionary	39.0	No corpus	New Testament
	50	Sowa	sowa1244	Short sketch	Dictionary	0.0	Translation	No Bible
	51	Apma	apma1240	Full grammar	Dictionary	16.5	Transcription	Bible parts
	52	Ske	seke1241	Long sketch	Dictionary	3.0	Interlinear	No Bible
53	Sa	saa1241	Long sketch	Long list	0.0	Interlinear	In progress	
Malekula	54	Vao-Vovo	vaoo1237	No grammar	Short list	2.0	No corpus	No Bible
	55	Mpotovoro	mpot1241	No grammar	Short list	1.0	No corpus	No Bible
	56	Nese	nese1235	Full grammar	Dictionary	3.0	Interlinear	No Bible
	57	Malua-Tepërav	malu1245	Long sketch	Short list	2.0	No corpus	No Bible
	58	Tirax	mace1241	Full grammar	Short list	4.0	Interlinear	No Bible
	59	Uripiv-Wala-Rano-Atchin	urip1239	Long sketch	Dictionary	13.0	Interlinear	NT with audio
60	Tape	mara1399	Long sketch	Dictionary	0.0	Interlinear	No Bible	

Region	Index	Language name	Glottocode	Grammar	Lexicon	Research score	Annotated corpus	Bible
Malekula (cont.)	61	V'ënen Taut	bign1238	Long sketch	Long list	4.5	Interlinear	Full Bible
	62	Naman	litz1237	Long sketch	Dictionary	3.0	No corpus	No Bible
	63	Larevet	lare1249	No grammar	Short list	1.0	No corpus	No Bible
	64	Neverver	ling1265	Full grammar	Short list	4.5	Interlinear	No Bible
	65	Nitita	niti1249	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	66	Neve'ei	vinm1237	Long sketch	Short list	3.0	No corpus	No Bible
	67	Unua	unua1237	Full grammar	Long list	13.0	Interlinear	No Bible
	68	Avava	katb1237	Long sketch	Dictionary	1.0	No corpus	No Bible
	69	Vivti	vivt1234	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	70	Rerep	rere1240	Short sketch	Long list	2.0	No corpus	Bible parts
	71	Dixon Reef	dixo1238	No grammar	Short list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	72	Bwenelang	bwen1239	No grammar	Long list	1.0	No corpus	No Bible
	73	Nasarian	nasa1240	No grammar	Long list	2.0	No corpus	No Bible
	74	Aulua	aulu1238	Short sketch	Long list	4.0	No corpus	Bible parts
	75	Nisvai	nisv1234	No grammar	Long list	1.0	Interlinear	No Bible
	76	Denggan	burm1263	Long sketch	Long list	5.0	Interlinear	No Bible
	77	Ninde	labo1244	Long sketch	Long list	4.0	Interlinear	Bible parts
	78	Letemboi-Repanbitip	lete1241	No grammar	Long list	1.0	No corpus	No Bible
	79	Nasvang	nasv1234	No grammar	Long list	1.0	No corpus	No Bible
	80	Nati	nati1244	Short sketch	Long list	3.0	No corpus	No Bible
	81	Ahamb	axam1237	Full grammar	Long list	10.0	Interlinear	Bible parts
	82	Lamap	port1285	Long sketch	Dictionary	9.0	No corpus	No Bible
	83	Navwien	navw1234	No grammar	Long list	0.0	No corpus	No Bible
	84	Uluveu	mask1242	Full grammar	Long list	2.0	No corpus	NT with audio
	85	Nahavaq	sout2857	Full grammar	Long list	4.0	No corpus	Bible parts
	86	Avok	avok1244	No grammar	Long list	2.0	No corpus	No Bible
	87	Na'ahai	malfl1237	No grammar	Long list	1.0	No corpus	Bible parts
AmbrymPaama	88	North Ambrym	nort2839	Long sketch	Dictionary	11.5	Interlinear	In progress
	89	Orkon-Fanbak	orko1234	No grammar	Short list	1.0	Interlinear	No Bible
	90	Lonwolwol	lonw1238	Long sketch	Dictionary	8.0	No corpus	Bible parts
	91	Dalkalaen	dalk1234	No grammar	Dictionary	1.0	Interlinear	No Bible
	92	Daakaka	daka1243	Full grammar	Dictionary	10.0	Interlinear	In progress
	93	Vatlongos	sout2859	Short sketch	Dictionary	23.0	Interlinear	NT with audio
	94	Daakie	port1286	No grammar	Dictionary	2.5	Interlinear	No Bible
95	Paama	paam1238	Full grammar	Dictionary	16.0	Interlinear	NT with audio	
Shefa	96	Lamenu	lame1260	Short sketch	Short list	4.0	No corpus	Bible parts
	97	Bierebo	bier1244	Full grammar	Short list	6.0	No corpus	No Bible
	98	Baki	baki1244	Short sketch	Short list	3.0	No corpus	NT with audio
	99	Maii	maii1238	No grammar	Short list	4.0	No corpus	No Bible
	100	Lewo	lewo1242	Full grammar	Long list	19.0	Translation	NT with audio
	101	Bieria	bier1246	Short sketch	Short list	3.0	No corpus	Bible parts
	102	Namakura	nama1268	Full grammar	Short list	7.0	Interlinear	In progress
	103	Fakamae	emae1237	Full grammar	Short list	5.0	Interlinear	No Bible
	104	Nakanamanga	nort2836	Short sketch	Dictionary	15.0	Interlinear	Full Bible
	105	Lelepa	lele1267	Full grammar	Short list	4.0	Interlinear	Bible parts
	106	Ifira-Mele	mele1250	Short sketch	Dictionary	6.0	Interlinear	New Testament
107	Nafsan	sout2856	Full grammar	Dictionary	11.0	Interlinear	New Testament	
108	Eton	eton1255	No grammar	Short list	1.0	Translation	No Bible	
Tafea	109	Ura	urav1235	Long sketch	Short list	10.0	No corpus	No Bible
	110	Ifo	ifoo1237	No grammar	Short list	4.0	No corpus	No Bible
	111	Sye	siee1239	Full grammar	Dictionary	15.0	No corpus	New Testament
	112	North Tanna	nort2847	Short sketch	Long list	6.0	No corpus	NT with audio
	113	Lenakel	lena1238	Long sketch	Dictionary	11.0	No corpus	NT with audio
	114	Whitesands	whit1269	Short sketch	Long list	16.5	Interlinear	NT with audio
	115	Futuna-Aniwa	futu1245	Long sketch	Dictionary	12.0	No corpus	New Testament
	116	Southwest Tanna	sout2869	Short sketch	Long list	4.0	No corpus	NT with audio
	117	Nafe	kwam1252	Short sketch	Dictionary	12.0	No corpus	NT with audio
	118	Aneityum	ane1239	Long sketch	Dictionary	18.0	No corpus	Full Bible